

**4PS (PAGAGALINGIN AT PAUUNLARIN ANG
PAG-AARAL SA PAGBASA): AN INTERVENTION TO
ENHANCE FILIPINO READING PERFORMANCE OF
GRADE 10 STUDENTS**

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4PS (Pagagalingin at Pauunlarin Ang Pag-aaral sa Pagbasa): An Intervention to Enhance Filipino Reading Performance of Grade 10 Students

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Abstract

This study aimed to determine the effect on the performance Project 4Ps (Pagagalingin at Pauunlarin ang Pag-aaral sa Pagbasa) and evaluate its implementation at Antonio C. Esguerra Memorial National High School during the school year 2023-2024. The researcher used experimental method of research utilizing pre-test and post-test were used to determine the level of reading performance of the students in selected competencies in Filipino 10. Likewise, descriptive method of research was employed with an adapted questionnaire-checklist as the main instrument which was administered to nine (9) teachers who served as respondents and who evaluated the reading program with respect to its objectives, instructional strategies, assessment, intervention activities, and monitoring and elevation. The results showed that There was a good increase on the scores of the students. With an overall total mean of 19.27 in the pretest, there was a vast difference of 20.23 resulting to an increase to 39.50. Moreso, the teacher-respondents provided positive evaluations on the conduct of reading remedial sessions. The teachers suggested that this program should be budgeted, use more reading techniques, and involve parents in the reading remedial session's process.

Keywords: *reading program, remedial sessions, filipino, grade 10 students, Philippines*

Introduction

Reading is one of the basic abilities that students should be taught and developed in. It is a fundamental learning tool and the foundation for all other learning. It improves one's ability to reason and think critically callously, distinguish, evaluate what has been read, and solve analytical difficulties.

In a similar vein, reading ability improves comprehension and analytical abilities. It piques the learners' imaginations and enhances their memory areas. As a result, it aids the retention of knowledge as well as the stabilization of an individual's emotions. As a result, it is critical to develop a reading habit to improve mental muscles. Reading is a great approach to learn about anything and everything. It aids in the discovery of new things and the education of individuals from all walks of life.

According to Aliponga (2013), reading becomes effective for the readers to achieve an overall understanding of what is described in the text rather than obtaining meaning in isolated words or sentences.

Reading is also considered by many people as a gratifying activity that broad one's knowledge and vocabulary. However, if one asks below-average learners of English whether they are reading, mostly, their answers are negative. Learners who are learning to read in English usually abhor it and spend limited time reading (Lituanas, et al., 2021).

The Department of Education Memorandum No. 173, s. 2019, "Hamon: Bawat Bata Bumabasa (3Bs Initiative) mandated to produce productive and responsible citizens equipped with essential competencies and skills for lifelong learning. Thus, to make every learner a proficient reader, schools across the country are tasked to help learners develop their reading skills. In addressing the gap, there is a need to strengthen the reading proficiency of every learner and nurture a culture of reading which is a requisite skill in all content areas.

In support of the Ten-Point Basic Education Agenda and the institutionalization of the "Every Child a Reader" Program (ECARP), the Department of Education (DepEd) is initiating programs that would promote reading and literacy among the pupils and students, motivate our youth to learn from the lives and works of eminent Filipinos, uphold one's own heritage and values; and make reading a shared physical experience, specifically among the youth, thereby increasing its relevance amidst the growing reliance on the internet and inclination to on-line activities (DepEd, 2011).

However, the level of difficulty in reading is ascending which has been considered as one of the major problems of teachers especially the reading teachers both in English and Filipino. If the child has poor reading, chances are his or her performance in any other subjects is poor and eventually affects learning (Dacalos, Datulayta, Davis, et al., 2016).

In 2018, at least 78 percent of students in the Philippines failed to reach minimum levels of proficiency in each of the three PISA subjects, with a wide gap by socioeconomic status. These results underscored the urgent need to address quality in basic education.

Here in the Philippines, upgrading the educational system, through the K to 12, is geared toward the improvement of quality education. To intensify these initiated programs of the DepEd to address reading needs of Filipino learners, policies and mandates were provided.

The Implementation of the Blue Rizal: Barangayan Para sa Bawat Bata Bumabasa (BR-B4) program is a response to the Department of Education's "Sulong Edukalidad" which aims to address the challenge of quality in basic education and to develop learners who are readers at the Grade level.

Cognizant to this is the conduct of reading remediation program at Antonio C. Esguerra Memorial National High School which is known as Project 4Ps (Pagagalangin at Pauunlarin ang Pag-aaral sa Pagbasa). This primarily aims to enhance the reading level of the students in Filipino through the conduct of series of reading remedial sessions.

In the desire to implement remedial reading program in response to great causes of the department, teachers cannot eliminate challenges encountered along the way. Best practices though were employed, but there were still students who were identified as frustrated readers or worst non-reader.

Because of this reason, the researcher opted to conduct this study to determine the effects of Project 4Ps in the performance of Grade 10 in Filipino. Likewise, this aimed to evaluate the implementation of the abovementioned project and determine the suggestions of the teachers to further improve the initiative.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the effects of Project 4Ps in the performance in reading of Grade 10 students at Antonio C. Esguerra Memorial National High School during the School Year 2023-2024. Specifically, it sought answers to the following research problems:

1. What is the level of performance of Grade 10 students as revealed in their pre-test and post-test results with respect to the following lessons:
 - 1.1 Sanhi at Bunga;
 - 1.2 Pagsasalaysay ng Buod;
 - 1.3 Kwentong Bayan'
 - 1.4 Paghihinuha ng Kalalabasan ng mga Pangyayari; and
 - 1.5 Kahulugan ng mga salitang di-pamilyar?
2. How do the teacher-respondents evaluate the implementation of Project 4Ps with respect to its:
 - 2.1. Objectives;
 - 2.2. Instructional Strategies;
 - 2.3. Assessment;
 - 2.4. Intervention Activities; and
 - 2.5. Project Monitoring and Evaluation?
3. What are the suggestions of the teacher-respondents to further improve the implementation of Project 4Ps?

Literature Review

Reading is essential to a person's life, especially to a child as this serves as key to wisdom and unlocks the gateway of imagination, pleasures, and glimpse of the world (Nedira, 2019). In addition, Reading is an active process in which readers interact with the text to reconstruct the message of the author give meaning based on their own experiences (Alcantara et al,2011). More so, Fosudo (2015) affirms that the acquisition of reading skills has a beneficial effect on all school subjects, including social studies, science, mathematics, and soon. Poor reading skill can make a child develop a poor attitude toward school and can create self-esteem problems later in life. Also, the teacher must know the nature of reading growth, the types of reading difficulties that might impede growth, and the characteristics of children that might predispose them to reading difficulties. Moreover, children grouped according to reading ability would not be similar in many other characteristics (Goldenberg, 2014).

Relatively, Feleo (2012) emphasized that it is must that every school should have a reading program which serves as follow-up to address reading problems especially the level of comprehension of the learners. Moreover, Lijano (2017) argued that it is essential for schools to not only give quality instruction to students, but also to reinforce the components of their engagement in learning, since they are the ultimate result of the entire educational learning process. This is especially significant since it suggests that classroom strategies may be applied to increase student motivation to learn. Furthermore, goal setting as a reading strategy to improve reading comprehension was the focus of the stud by Shih and Reynolds (2018), as they integrated goal setting into reading instruction. They argued that when compared with the traditional teaching, goal setting integrated reading strategy resulted in better reading comprehension of students. Moreover, it was found that the strategy encourages readers' motivation, autonomy, and self-efficacy.

Methodology

Research Design

Experimental and descriptive method of research was used in the study to determine the level of performance in reading of Grade 10

students and evaluation of the teacher-respondents on the implementation of Project 4Ps.

According to Harland (2020) explained that experimental method of research is a controlled procedure that sees the manipulation of an independent variable to observe and measure any effect this has on a dependent variable. The essential features of the experimental method are then the control, observation and measurement of variables.

This design was suitable in this study since the researcher aimed to describe the performance of the students after being exposed to the reading remedial sessions.

Meanwhile, Siedlecki (2020), in descriptive research, researchers studied the variables as they appear in their natural context and no manipulation is done. Survey questionnaire is used in descriptive method which is useful for collecting information from a group to describe characteristics of the population. In addition, it involves the collection and analysis of data about people or materials with the intention to compare existing and required standards.

This was appropriate to the study since it also aimed to determine the evaluation of the teachers on the implementation of Project 4Ps.

Sampling

The student-respondents were chosen based on the results of their first quarter examination in Filipino 10. The forty-four (44) students were selected using purposive sampling technique. A purposive sample is a non-probability sample that is selected based on characteristics of a population and the objective of the study. Purposive sampling is also known as judgmental, selective, or subjective sampling.

The samples from the total number of populations were chosen based on the scores in their exam. They were those who failed in the assessment test and got lowest scores in reading competencies in Filipino.

Meanwhile, the nine (9) teacher-respondents were chosen using the purposive-complete enumeration sampling. These teachers are Filipino teachers who are also reading teachers who conducted reading remediation sessions. They were asked to assess the implementation of Project 4Ps based on the cited aspects.

Data Collection

The researcher used two instruments in gathering necessary data. The first instrument was the researcher-made pre-test and post-test. These were content validated before the administration to measure the level of performance of the students before and after exposure to the reading remedial sessions.

The other research instrument was the adapted questionnaire checklist from the study of Cariño, Villagracia, and Reyes (2022). It was utilized to evaluate the reading program in terms of its objectives, instructional strategies, assessment, intervention activities, program monitoring and evaluation.

Results and Discussion

Level of Performance in Selected Lessons in Filipino of Grade 10 Students

Table 1 presents the level of performance in selected lessons in Filipino of Grade 10 students as revealed in the results of the pre-test and post-test.

Table 1. Level of Performance of Grade 10 Students

Score	Verbal Interpretation	Pretest		Posttest	
		F	%	F	%
50	Outstanding	-	-	-	-
37-48	Very Satisfactory	-	-	33	75.0
25-36	Satisfactory	1	2.3	11	25.0
13-24	Fairly Satisfactory	43	97.7		0.0
1-12	Did not meet expectations	-	-	-	-
Total		44	100.0	44	100.0
Highest Score			26		42
Lowest Score			15		25
Mean			19.272		39.500
MPS			38.544		79.00
Std. Deviation			3.060		5.192

It can be seen on the table that with the same given 50-item test in both Pre-test and Post-test, the gathered data revealed a good result. There was a good increase on the scores of the students. With an overall total mean of 19.27 in the pretest, there was a vast difference of 20.23 resulting to an increase to 39.50. This means that the reading remedial sessions in Filipino played significant effect on the performance of Grade 10 in selected competencies in Filipino 10.

This implies that Project 4Ps can enhance and develop the reading skills of the students.

Evaluations of Teachers on the Implementation of 4Ps with respect to Selected Aspects

Table 2 presents the evaluation of teacher-respondents on the implementation of Project 4Ps with respect to its objectives.

It can be glanced on the table that the evaluation of the teacher-respondents on the implementation of Project 4Ps in terms of objective gained an overall mean of 3.58 and verbally interpreted as Much Agree.

Table 2. Evaluation of the Teacher-Respondents on the Implementation of Project 4Ps in terms of Its Objectives

<i>Objectives</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
1. The program develops love for reading among students.	3.78	Much Agree
2. The program enhances the literacy skills of the learners.	3.44	Much Agree
3. The program motivates the students through reading which lead to their increased academic performance.	3.33	Much Agree
4. The program trains the reading-teachers regarding the process.	3.78	Much Agree
5. The program establishes strong collaboration among stakeholders.	3.56	Much Agree
Overall Mean	3.58	Much Agree

The result suggests that the teachers believed that the reading program in Filipino attained its set goals as regards enhancement of reading skills of the students in Filipino particularly the targeted competencies. This implies that Project 4Pserved its purpose as reading remedial program.

Table 3 presents the evaluation of teacher-respondents on the implementation of Project 4Ps with respect to its instructional strategies.

It can be glanced on the table that the evaluation of the teacher-respondents on the implementation of Project 4Ps in terms of instructional strategies gained an overall mean of 3.47 and verbally interpreted as Much Agree.

Table 3. Evaluation of the Teacher-Respondents on the Implementation of Project 4Ps in terms of Its Instructional Strategies

<i>Instructional Strategies</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
1. The program provides differentiated instruction to different types of readers.	3.44	Much Agree
2. The program provides different materials for diverse learners.	3.56	Much Agree
3. The program designs appropriate reading lessons to meet readers' needs.	3.33	Much Agree
4. The program utilizes picture clues and illustrations to aid the pupils in reading.	3.22	Agree
5. The program uses explicit instruction on critical reading priorities.	3.78	Much Agree
Overall Mean	3.47	Much Agree

The result suggests that the teachers concurred to the idea that the reading program in Filipino employed variety of strategies during the conduct of reading remedial sessions. This implies that the Project 4Ps aided the students who are struggling in selected reading competencies through utilization of different strategies which addressed the learning styles of the learners.

Table 4 presents the evaluation of teacher-respondents on the implementation of Project 4Ps with respect to its assessment.

It can be glanced on the table that the evaluation of the teacher-respondents on the implementation of Project 4Ps in terms of assessment gained an overall mean of 3.22 and verbally interpreted as Agree.

The result suggests that the teachers accorded that the reading program in Filipino included assessment of learning in the remedial sessions. It can also be noted that majority of indicators fell under Agree which means that this part of the program can still be improved.

This implies that Project 4Ps utilized assessment tools to measure the level of performance of the clientele which served as the bases to record their progress before, during, and after the conduct of remedial sessions.

Table 4. *Evaluation of the Teacher-Respondents on the Implementation of Project 4Ps in terms of Its Assessment*

<i>Assessment</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
1. The program implementers use the prescribed assessment tools from the DepEd.	3.00	Agree
2. The program implementers give assessment at the beginning, during the implementation, and after the conduct of the program.	3.11	Agree
3. The program implementers observe and record learner's progress before, during, and after the implementation.	3.22	Agree
4. The program implementers reflect on the results of the assessment tests.	3.56	Much Agree
5. The program implementers report the analysis of the results of the assessment tests.	3.22	Agree
Overall Mean	3.22	Agree

Table 5 presents the evaluation of teacher-respondents on the implementation of Project 4Ps with respect to its intervention activities.

Table 5. *Evaluation of the Teacher-Respondents on the Implementation of Project 4Ps in terms of Its Intervention Activities*

<i>Intervention Activities</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
1. The program implementers include language activities that develop reading, listening, speaking, and writing skills of the learners.	3.44	Much Agree
2. The program builds phonemic awareness activities into instruction in letter and sounds.	3.44	Much Agree
3. The program gives intervention activities that improve learner's vocabulary.	3.56	Much Agree
4. The program uses tutoring or small group instruction for children who require additional instructional support.	3.44	Much Agree
5. The program stimulates the pupils' interest in reading through interactive reading activities.	3.67	Much Agree
Overall Mean	3.51	Much Agree

It can be glanced on the table that the evaluation of the teacher-respondents on the implementation of Project 4Ps in terms of intervention activities gained an overall mean of 3.51 and verbally interpreted as Much Agree.

The results suggest that the reading program in Filipino offered various learning tasks that would enhance the reading performance of the students. This implies that Project 4Ps allows the students to master the target competencies in reading through engaging them in intervention activities.

Table 6 presents the evaluation of teacher-respondents on the implementation of Project 4Ps with respect to its intervention activities.

It can be glanced on the table that the evaluation of the teacher-respondents on the implementation of Project 4Ps in terms of monitoring and evaluation gained an overall mean of 2.98 and verbally interpreted as Agree. It can be reflected from the results that the indicators of this variable all obtained mean under Agree. This suggests that the respondents believed that the reading program was monitored and evaluated. On the other note, it also suggests that the proponent can still employ strategies that can enhance the monitoring scheme of Project 4Ps. This implies that the reading program in Filipino used frameworks that would identify the strengths and weaknesses of its process.

Table 6. Evaluation of the Teacher-Respondents on the Implementation of Project 4Ps in terms of Its Monitoring and Evaluation

<i>Monitoring and Evaluation</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
1. The reading-teachers strictly monitor the process from the start to its completion.	3.00	Agree
2. The reading-teachers conduct risk analysis relative to every aspect of the program.	3.11	Agree
3. The reading-teachers identify plans for the continuous improvement of the program	3.11	Agree
4. The reading-teachers discuss the progress of the reading program among teachers and stakeholders.	3.00	Agree
5. The reading-teachers provide periodic and timely feedback on the conduct of intervention activities.	2.67	Agree
Overall Mean	2.98	Agree

Suggestions of the Teachers to further improve the Implementation of Project 4Ps

Based on the answers of the teachers, the following are the frequent suggestions of the respondents for further improvement of the reading program. First, teachers should provide / use more technique in reading. Also, the reading materials should be attractive to the readers. Likewise, the reading materials shall be appropriate for their age or level and contain moral lessons. Furthermore, parents should have a deeper involvement in this program. Therefore, there should be follow up at home since the teachers have so many tasks to do. Lastly, reading should be strictly implemented every Friday to help students develop their skills as well as their comprehension in reading.

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